

Factors Affecting Audit Quality in Vietnam

Author's Details: ⁽¹⁾Thi Ngoc Thuy Tran ⁽²⁾Thi Hoa Le ⁽³⁾Thi My Pham

⁽¹⁾⁽²⁾⁽³⁾University of Economics - Technology for Industries, Vietnam

Correspondence: Thi Ngoc Thuy Tran, 456 Minh Khai, Hai Ba Trung, Ha Noi

Abstract:

The first study in Vietnam evaluated the factors affecting the audit quality of SAV's financial statements for audited banks, in which the factors affecting the audit quality were grouped based on subjects. The audit includes the group of factors belonging to the SAV, the group of factors belonging to the SAV, and the group of factors from outside. Such grouping has covered all the factors mentioned in previous studies, taking into account the context of the SAV.

Keywords: Auditing quality, state audit, Vietnam

1. Introduction

On June 24, 2015, at the 9th session, XIII National Assembly, voted to pass the Law on State Audit (SAV) and takes effect from January 1, 2016. Accordingly, the Law on State Audit 2015 clearly stipulates that the audited object of SAV is the management and use of public finance, public property and activities related to the management and use of public finance, public assets of the units. audit. With the functions and duties of the current SAV, the SAV plays an important role in confirming the correctness and honesty of the financial situation of banks as well as having the function of managing and supervising the implementation of regulations. law on the management and use of public finance and public assets of banks.

In addition, the strengthening of the audits of banks also stems from the fact that requires improving the operational efficiency of the entire national financial system; stemming from the public's demands on public disclosure, information transparency and effective government management and public resources. Reality shows that social public opinion in recent times has many concerns about the quality of the banks' operations, a series of economic cases causing particularly serious consequences related to banks, billions The high bad debt ratio reduces the public's confidence in the banking system, affecting the stability of the state's macroeconomic situation. SAV is an effective tool to inspect, evaluate comprehensively and improve the economy, effectiveness and efficiency of banks in order to properly implement the goals and policies of socio-economic development of the country. Assembly, Government, at the same time making the national financial system healthy.

2. Literature review

2.1. Researches on audit quality

Auditing has been around since feudal times when kings needed special people to inspect local governments and merchants. Modern auditing also began in 1844 when the British Parliament passed the Law on Joint Stock Companies, forcing business directors to audit financial data before disclosing information to shareholders. However, it was not until the beginning of the 20th century that the issue of quality and efficiency of audit activities began to be concerned, when a new law on joint stock companies (Companies Act) was enacted at He requires that reporting the financial statements of joint stock companies must be done by an independent auditor (Teck-Heang and Ali, 2008).

The first study dealing directly with the concept of audit quality was performed by DeAngelo in 1981 under the title "Auditor size and audit quality". According to DeAngelo, audit quality is the auditor's ability to detect material misstatements in a customer's accounting system and to report such material misstatement. Thus, the concept of audit quality from DeAngelo's point of view includes two aspects. One is that the auditor's ability to detect material misstatement in the client's accounting system depends on the effectiveness of the audit process

and the professional capacity of the auditor. Second, the auditor's report on such violation depends on the auditor's sense of compliance with ethical standards and the auditor's independence from the business. Angelo's views are later on Palmrose (1988), Bradshaw (2001) and most scientific researches on auditing.

Also in his research, DeAngelo studied the relationship between the size of the audit firm and audit quality. By examining published studies of various scholars from 1967-1981, DeAngelo found that the clients of small auditing firms (few employees, few customers and few assets). often with the frequency of changing auditing firms more often than the customers of large auditing firms. The reason is that small audit firms often have a lower negotiating position and lower independence, customers can influence the coming of audit conclusions. In addition, small audit firms often have less audit experience, both in time and space than large companies, so the ability to propose solutions to improve the accounting system of clients. lower rows (Coe and Palmon, 1979). The above two factors cause a high rate of small auditing firms being replaced by customers. In contrast, a large-scale audit company, with a large number of auditors and customers can provide audit services with better quality, a higher negotiating position because of a large number of customers, Auditing firms do not have to give in when making audit conclusions to retain only one customer (DeAngelo, 1981).

Although DeAngelo's study only looked at the impact of one factor affecting audit quality (auditor size) and did not use quantitative methods to measure specific impacts, this is considered the first study to lay the foundation for future audit quality studies. DeAngelo's contribution was great when giving the concept of audit quality and the methodology that synthesized studies on the relationship between audit performance and conflicts of interest (conflicts of interest) between auditors and company leadership.

Many later scholars have inherited and developed DeAngelo's idea, built a measurement model and proposed new elements. Mock and Samet (1982) surveyed auditors in the US with 32 criteria to evaluate the quality of the audit and concluded that there are five factors that affect audit quality, including: Planning, Management Management, Procedure, Assessment, and Practice. All these factors affect the same direction to audit quality. Although the research of Mock and Samet inherited did not develop a new concept of audit quality proposed by DeAngelo, the two scholars have built a methodology and a basic model to evaluate the impact of these influencing factors. new enjoyment. Some later scholars have used similar models of Mock and Samet to test the factors with different samples. For example, Sutton and Lampe (1991) surveyed the direct auditors participating in many audits in the US to develop the audit quality assessment model of Mock and Samet with 19 factors and conclusions. Three main factors affecting audit quality include Planning, Customer Auditing Process and Auditing Management.

Sutton's 1993 study surveyed experienced auditors to develop and identify factors that affect audit quality for similar results.

The studies of Mock and Samet (1982), Sutton and Lampe (1991), although inheriting DeAngelo's approach, it is the measurement of audit quality by the factors that determine the probability of false detection and reporting. However, in the conclusion of the studies mentioned, only the factors that belong to the auditors belong to the auditors. According to DeAngelo, these factors only affect the first aspect of audit quality, which is the ability of the auditor to detect material misstatements in the client's accounting system. Thus, the study of Mock and Samet or Sutton and Lampe did not find out the factors affecting the second aspect is the ability of auditors to report on such material mistakes.

Many scholars in this same period systematized the factors affecting audit quality to create a reasonable basis for measuring those factors. Schoroeder et al. (1982), on the basis of two aspects proposed by DeAngelo, classify the factors affecting audit quality into two groups including those belonging to the audit / auditor group and other factors that affect audit quality. The factor belongs to the auditing company. Also at the 1982 study by Schroeder et al. Entitled "Audit Quality: The Perception of Audit-Committee Chairpersons and Audit Partners" , the research team has surveyed the audit committee and auditors to identify 15 factors that affect the quality of the audit and conclude that, the group of factors that belong to the auditor / audit group is important. than the

group of factors belongs to the auditing company. Thus, while Mock and Samet's research concludes on audit firm factors, Schoreder et al.

Conclusion in the study of Schroeder et al. (1982) was developed by many later scholars and gave similar results. Carcello et al (1992) in the study "Audit Quality Attributes: The Perceptions of Audit Partners, Preparers, and Financial Statement Users" (The attributes of audit quality: Perceptions of auditors, auditing firms and users of financial statements have also concluded that most of the key influencing factors identified are Council Experience, Industry Experience, Responsiveness Client Responsiveness, A sense of compliance with GAAS standards (Ethical standards). The study was conducted by surveying financial reporters, auditors and users of financial statements in the US with 41 criteria belonging to 12 groups of factors affecting audit quality.

While the studies of Mock and Samet (1982), Sutton and Lampe (1991) only approach one object to evaluate the factors affecting audit quality (auditors), the study of Carcello together colleagues (1992) addressed a broader target group. Later, the study of Alhizer et al. (1995), Warming-Rasmussen and Jensen (1998) and some other scholars also used a similar approach in their studies and found some factors. other influences, such as Independence (Warming-Rasmussen and Jensen, 1998) or Dure care (Aldhizer et al., 1995).

It can be seen that, in the period before 2000, most researchers later tried to evaluate more and more factors related to auditing activities and affect the quality of auditing financial statements. Karma. In a long study published in 2004 by Angus Duff entitled "Auditqual: Dimensions of audit quality", the factors that influence audit quality are fully covered and systematized in a broader approach. Specifically, according to Angus Duff, audit quality includes two aspects: (1) Professional quality and (2) Quality of service. Firstly, professional quality is a group of technical factors and is directly related to audit activities such as Company position (reputation, size), Independence, Competence (Skills, experience) . Second, service quality relates to factors outside of the audit of financial statements, such as Ability to meet customer needs, Ability to provide non-audit services (financial consulting, restructuring), Understand customers (empathy, service).

In addition to the efforts to develop multiple models and introduce more and more new influencers, many studies also use old models to evaluate one (or a few) factors that influence many studies. confirmed, but in different geographical spaces. The most frequently considered factors include Audit team and audit firm experience with clients (Chen et al., 2001), Career skills / Professional expertise (Behn et al., 1999; Pandit, 1999; Chen et al., 2000), Audit firm response to customer needs (Behn et al., 1999; Chen et al., 2000), Audit firm size accounting (Alpaslan Yasar, 2013), Reputation of auditing firms (Nichols and Smith, 1983; Craswell, Francis, and Taylor, 1995).

Developing the views of many scholars, organizations, and associations of practicing accounting and auditing around the world also build a full framework (framework) to evaluate the quality of audit activities. In the framework of the International Auditing and Assurance Standards Board (IAASB) announced in 2013, the audit quality is considered comprehensively, including the elements from the beginning. Input (Attitude and ethics of the auditor / audit team; knowledge and experience of the auditor; audit performance and quality control procedures of the audit company), output (calculation the sustainability of the audit relationship between the auditor and the customer, the level of customer satisfaction), to the external environment (the legal system of accounting - auditing). The Audit Quality Framework announced in 2008 by the Financial Reporting Council (FRC) covers five aspects of audit quality assurance, including (1) culture in public. (working environment, fairness, honesty are highly valued), (2) Professional quality and skills of auditors and audit directors, (3) The effectiveness of the audit process , (4) Usefulness of audit reports, (5) External factors do not depend on the auditor. The Public Company Accounting Oversight Board (PCAOB) also proposes similar frameworks for audit quality.

Thus, the majority of research on audit quality are consensus and develop from the concept of audit quality proposed by DeAngelo and develop in an approach to analyzing the factors associated with different

stakeholders. process as well as use audit results. On that basis, international organizations and associations of accounting and auditing practice have developed a complete framework with index systems to evaluate audit quality, notably. Financial Reporting Council (FRC) or International Auditing Standards and Assurance Services Committee (IAASB), International Auditing Practice Committee (IAPC), British Association of Certified Public Accountants (ACCA) , Association of Chartered Accountants of England and Wales (ICAEW).

2.2. State Audit Studies

State audit is firstly established in a number of forms to serve the requirement of proper and reasonable use of national financial resources when consumed for socio-economic activities. Today, with the strong development of the global market economy, the state audit plays an increasingly important role as the supreme public financial inspection agency, which helps a lot for sustainable development. of a nation. Based on the specific political institutions of each country, the state audit agency will have different organizational forms and modes of operation, but all have a common name as the Supreme Audit Institution (Supreme Audit Institution). - WRONG). For example: Court of Appraisal of the Republic of France, United States General Accountants Agency, Audit Office of Russian Federation, Korea Audit and Audit Commission, British Auditing Agency; Japan Auditing Committee; ... Most of the regions in the world set up the Organization of the Supreme Auditing Body according to each region. At the same time, nearly 200 countries join the International Organization of Supreme Audit Institutions-INTOSAI). The role of the SAV is very important, but currently there are very few studies in the world on this topic. Researches on state audit often revolve around clarifying the role or analyzing aspects and problems arising in the government audit. Clark et al. (2007) "Audit quality attributes of European Union supreme audit institutions" can be considered typical. This study was conducted on SAIs of 25 member countries from the European Union

– EU with data on 30 issues related to accountability and direct independence from the permissible law of these SAIs. Among them, some issues related to SAI's parliamentary accountability such as: appointing SAI head office, state audit annual work plan, right to request auditors , ... Some issues related to SAI's independence from the government such as: the independence specified in the law, the full authority to collect necessary information for the audit, not being governed and directed. from anyone,... The results indicate that in addition to some cases where the law allows to remain silent, the provisions generally provide for the full independence of SAIs from the governing body. In addition, SAIs' accountability provisions before parliament appear weaker in some ways. Finally, the authors also expressed the view that the research was exploited based on permissible laws from the EU member states and may, practice and conventions do not completely reflect the application The law will make it possible for SAIs to have as little or more independence or accountability as the results obtained.

Research by Zdyrko (2016) "Problem aspects of internal state audit development" focuses on highlighting the situation of national financial management in Ukraine. Based on the analysis of statistics from internal audit in 2015 of Ukraine exploited from the State Audit Agency of Ukraine, the author pointed out some prominent problems such as: (1) the shortage in the subdivisions that handle internal audits; (2) a lack of guaranteed functional and organizational freedom in the state audit departments; (3) gaps in the internal audit implementation plan; (4) Deficiencies in the fulfillment of the auditor's performance, as well as in the quality of the reports associated with the implementation of the internal audit and the validity of findings based on the relevant results. . Since then, Zdyrko (2016) argued that in order to ensure the relevance and effectiveness of state audit, it is necessary to (1) demonstrate the professional skills of state auditors, (2) to increase the number of internal audit units; (3) there is a need for a clear division of functions and duties between public auditors to avoid conflicts, (4) laws and regulations defining responsibility for violations of many financial disciplines also require must be significantly revised.

Synthesis of domestic and foreign studies can be seen that, the research on the quality of the auditing of financial statements of commercial banks in Vietnam is still relatively poor, and mainly the research is under

the angle of of independent audit. Besides, there are very few researches on state audit in the world and in Vietnam, the studies only focus on the role of SAV. Thus, there is currently a lack of research to build a theoretical framework on audit quality, as well as a lack of research on measuring and testing the factors that affect the quality of auditing financial statements from the perspective. of the State Audit. Independent audit means auditing activities of enterprises according to the provisions of law and auditing for all units and individuals that have audit needs (voluntary objects). Unlike independent auditing, State Audit audits units and individuals operating on the basis of the State budget. According to the 2015 Law on SAV, the function of the SAV is to evaluate, confirm, conclude and recommend for the management and use of public finance and public assets. In which: Public finance includes: State budget; national reserve; off-budget state financial funds; finance of state agencies, people's armed forces units, public non-business units, service providers, public goods, political organizations, socio-political organizations, major organizations socio-occupational governance, social organizations, socio-professional organizations using state funds and funds; state capital share in enterprises; public debt. Public assets include: land; Water Resources; natural resources; resources in the sea, airspace; other natural resources; State property in state agencies, people's armed forces units, public non-business units, political organizations, socio-political organizations, socio-political-professional organizations, social organizations associations, socio-professional organizations; public assets are assigned to businesses for management and use; state reserve assets; infrastructure assets in service of the public interest and other property invested and managed by the State shall be under the ownership of the entire people, represented and uniformly managed by the State. Therefore, evaluating the audit quality as well as measuring the factors affecting the auditing quality of financial statements from the perspective of the State Auditor will have many differences compared to the perspective of the independent auditor. create.

3. Research method

Quantitative method: The thesis analyzes quantitatively based on primary data collected through the questionnaire and SPSS 26.0 software to see the relationship of 12 factors to audit quality, thereby pointing out the Which is the most important, which factor is less important in improving the quality of auditing financial statements of the SAV. Specific quantitative methods include: Cronbach's Alpha reliability test method, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), CFA (Confirmatory) factor analysis), linear regression method (Regression Model).

In addition to the qualitative and quantitative methods as described above, the research also uses other methods such as comparison method, synthesis method, description method, ...

4. Result

By using SPSS 26.0 software and calculating Cronbach's Alpha coefficients of each sub-factor to examine the appropriateness of sub-factors in the same factor group. Cronbach's Alpha of the higher the child factors, the better the observational variables are very good and the traits of the parent factor. According to the research results of Nunnally (1978), the values of Cronbach Alpha coefficients above 0.8 are very good.

Table 1. Test results of Cronbach's Alpha reliability

variables	correlation of total variables	Cronbach' Alpha
Nangluc: Cronbach' Alpha = 0,828, N=4		
Nangluc1	0,648	0,786
Nangluc2	0,682	0,771
Nangluc3	0,643	0,788
Nangluc4	0,646	0,788
Chuyenmon: Cronbach' Alpha = 0,829, N=4		

Chuyenmon1	0,698	0,764
Chuyenmon2	0,670	0,778
Chuyenmon3	0,614	0,803
Chuyenmon4	0,642	0,791
Kinhnghiem: Cronbach' Alpha = 0,835, N=5		
Kinhnghiem1	0,665	0,794
Kinhnghiem2	0,642	0,800
Kinhnghiem3	0,601	0,811
Kinhnghiem4	0,634	0,803
Kinhnghiem5	0,635	0,802
Tuanthu: Cronbach' Alpha = 0,885, N=5		
Tuanthu1	0,711	0,863
Tuanthu2	0,720	0,861
Tuanthu3	0,731	0,858
Tuanthu4	0,727	0,860
Tuanthu5	0,725	0,860
Thantrong: Cronbach' Alpha = 0,890, N=5		
Thantrong1	0,752	0,861
Thantrong2	0,741	0,863
Thantrong3	0,674	0,878
Thantrong4	0,750	0,861
Thantrong5	0,738	0,864
Doclap: Cronbach' Alpha = 0,847, N=4		
Doclap1	0,666	0,814
Doclap2	0,701	0,799
Doclap3	0,678	0,809
Doclap4	0,694	0,802
DKLV: Cronbach' Alpha = 0,946, N=6		
DKLV1	0,817	0,938
DKLV2	0,828	0,937
DKLV3	0,826	0,937
DKLV4	0,834	0,936
DKLV5	0,865	0,933
DKLV6	0,846	0,935
Phuongphap: Cronbach' Alpha = 0,834, N=4		
Phuongphap1	0,675	0,786
Phuongphap2	0,706	0,772
Phuongphap3	0,650	0,797
Phuongphap4	0,626	0,807
KSCL: Cronbach' Alpha = 0,889, N=6		
KSCL1	0,714	0,868
KSCL2	0,685	0,872
KSCL3	0,722	0,866
KSCL4	0,662	0,876

KSCL5	0,739	0,864
KSCL6	0,706	0,869
Nganhang: Cronbach' Alpha = 0,901, N=6		
Nganhang1	0,745	0,881
Nganhang2	0,728	0,884
Nganhang3	0,759	0,879
Nganhang4	0,729	0,884
Nganhang5	0,702	0,888
Nganhang6	0,718	0,885
Phaply: Cronbach' Alpha = 0,883, N=4		
Phaply1	0,758	0,845
Phaply2	0,734	0,854
Phaply3	0,737	0,853
Phaply4	0,752	0,847
Ngoaikhac: Cronbach' Alpha = 0,343, N=2		
Ngoaikhac1	0,207	.
Ngoaikhac2	0,207	.

The results showed that all 53 observed variables of 11 factors downloaded the same 11 factors with Eigen-Value > 1 and the KMO test results reached 0.936, much higher than the required level 0.5. The Bartlett test is significant at $p = 0.000$, proving that the prudent factor measurement data used for factor analysis is completely appropriate, the observed variables are correlated with each other and statistically significant. Thus, all 53 observed variables met the requirements and included them for testing with CFA analysis.

Table 2. Rotation matrix of independent factors

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
DKLV5	0,823										
DKLV2	0,793										
DKLV4	0,791										
DKLV6	0,789										
DKLV3	0,784										
DKLV1	0,760										
Nganhang3		0,735									
Nganhang2		0,724									
Nganhang1		0,713									
Nganhang4		0,711									
Nganhang6		0,697									
Nganhang5		0,646									
KSCL5			0,690								
KSCL2			0,657								
KSCL1			0,656								
KSCL4			0,653								
KSCL3			0,612								

KSCL6			0,599								
Thantrong4				0,786							
Thantrong2				0,745							
Thantrong5				0,728							
Thantrong1				0,727							
Thantrong3				0,615							
Tuanthu2					0,708						
Tuanthu4					0,705						
Tuanthu3					0,696						
Tuanthu5					0,645						
Tuanthu1					0,643						
Kinhnghiem1						0,726					
Kinhnghiem2						0,640					
Kinhnghiem5						0,626					
Kinhnghiem4						0,626					
Kinhnghiem3						0,608					
Phaply4							0,705				
Phaply2							0,696				
Phaply1							0,667				
Phaply3							0,627				
Doclap4								0,670			
Doclap3								0,670			
Doclap2								0,662			
Doclap1								0,618			
Phuongphap2									0,659		
Phuongphap4									0,630		
Phuongphap1									0,622		
Phuongphap3									0,576		
Chuyenmon1										0,610	
Chuyenmon2										0,597	
Chuyenmon3										0,590	
Chuyenmon4										0,572	
Nangluc2											0,621
Nangluc3											0,590
Nangluc4											0,558
Nangluc1											0,557

Next we analyze the CFA results

1.118 chiquare/df
 .021 rmsea
 .982 cfi
 .846 gfi
 .826 agfi
 .002 p
 1270 df

The results show the factors affecting the quality of auditing financial statements at banks, including 3 groups of factors: the group of factors belonging to the foreign auditor (Professional Competence, Professional Skills, Working experience, Compliance with SAV standards, Careful care and confidentiality, Integrity, independence and objectivity), the group of factors belongs to the audit unit (Working conditions of Auditor, Method / Auditing process, Auditing quality control system of SAV) and other factors (Factors belong to audited banks, factors belong to the legal environment for audit activities). The quantitative analysis results show that the above factors all directly affect the audit quality of SAV when performing audits at banks. In which, the factors of the quality control system of the SAV, the audit methods / processes and the professional factors of the auditor are the three factors that most strongly affect the quality of the audit.

Therefore, a number of recommendations have been proposed to improve the quality of auditing financial statements at banks performed by the SAV. The solutions include: (1) improving the quality of audit quality

control activities, (2) improving audit methods and processes, (3) building and strengthening the professional capacity of the team. (4) improve the requirements on professional ethics of the auditor, (5) improve the working conditions of the auditor. At the same time, solutions are also given for banks to improve their governance based on the results from audit reports, in particular: (1) seriously implementing audit recommendations. on legal compliance, financial management, public assets, (2) improving the quality of financial statements, (3) strengthening credit management, (4) building an audit system modern internal management system, (5) applying modern information technology trends. Research results still have limitations, but this will be the orientation to develop further research on audit quality.

5. Conclusion

The basic contents of the Strategic Framework for the development of the SAV for the period 2020-2035 and a vision to 2035 include 8 contents: Completing the legal basis for the organization and operation of the SAV; Strategy for developing the organizational apparatus system of SAV; Human resource development strategy; Strategy to improve audit quality; Strategy for international integration and cooperation; Development strategy for material foundations, information, propaganda and scientific research; IT development strategy. Thus, we can see the importance of the SAV's audit quality improvement because the quality is decisive in asserting the prestige, effectiveness and efficiency of the SAV's operations.

References

- i. *Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (BCBS), 2004. Basel II: International Convergence of Capital Measurement and Capital Standards: A Revised Framework - Comprehensive Version.*
- ii. *Beaver, W. H., Ryan, S. G., & Wahlen, J. M., 1997. When is "bad news" viewed as "good news"?, Financial Analysis Journal, Vol 53, Issue 1, 45–54.*
- iii. *Boon, K., McKinnon, J., & Ross, P., 2008. Audit service quality in compulsory audit tendering, Accounting Research Journal.*
- iv. *Behn, B.K., Carcello, J.V., Hermanson, D.R. and Hermanson, R.H., 1997. The Determinants of Audit Client Satisfaction among Clients of Big 6 Firms, Accounting Horizons, American Accounting Association, 7–24.*
- v. *Bradshaw, M. T., Richardson, S. A., & Sloan, R. G., 2001. Do Analysts and Auditors Use Information in Accruals?, Journal of Accounting and Research, Vol 39, Issue 1, 45 – 74.*
- vi. *Carcello, J. V., Hermanson, R. H., & McGrath, N. T., 1992. Audit Quality Attributes: The Perceptions of Audit Partners, Preparers, and Financial Statement Users, Auditing: A Journal of Practice and Theory, 11(1), 1- 15.*
- vii. *Chen, C. Y., Lin, C. J., & Lin, Y. C., 2008. Audit Partner Tenure, Audit Firm Tenure, and Discretionary Accruals: Does Longterm Auditor Tenure Impair Earnings Quality?, Contemporary Accounting Research, Vol 25, Issue 2, 415 – 445.*
- viii. *Coe, T. L., & Palmon, D., 1979. Some evidence of the magnitude of auditor turnover, Unpublished manuscript, New York University, New York.*
- ix. *Collins, J. H., Shackelford, D. A., & Wahlen, J. M., 1995. Bank differences in the coordination of regulatory capital, earnings, and taxes, Accounting Research, Vol 33, Issue 2, 263–291.*
- x. *Craswell, A. T., Francis, J. R., & Taylor, S. L. , 1995. Auditor brand name reputations and industry specialisations, Journal of Accounting and Economics, 20(3), 297-322.*
- xi. *Cushing, J. M., 1989. A competition model for size-structured species, SIAM Journal on Applied Mathematics, 49(3), 838-858.*
- xii. *DeAngelo, L. E., 1981. Auditor Size and Audit Quality, Journal of Accounting and Economics, 3, 183 – 199.*
- xiii. *Duff, A., 2004. Auditqual: Dimensions of Audit Quality, The Institute of Chartered Accountants of Scotland.*
- xiv. *Financial Reporting Council (FRC), 2006. Promoting audit quality: Discussion Paper, London.*

- xv. Francis, J.R., 2011. A framework for understanding and researching audit quality, *Auditing: A Journal of Practice & Theory*, 30 (2), 125 - 152.
- xvi. Greenawalt, M. B., & Sinkey, J. F. , 1988. Bank loan-loss provisions and the income-smoothing hypothesis: An empirical analysis, 1976 – 1984, *Journal of Financial Services Research*, Vol 1, Issue 4, 301 – 318.
- xvii. Healy, P. M., & Wahlen, J. M., 1999. A review of the earnings management literature and its implications for standard setting, *Accounting Horizons*, Vol 13, Issue 4, 365–383.
- xviii. International Auditing and Assurance Standards Board (IAASB), 2013. A framework for Audit Quality, New York.
- xix. International Auditing and Assurance Standards Board (IAASB), 2013. Audit quality: An IAASB Perspective, New York.
- xx. Kanagaretnam, K., Krishnan, G. V., & Lobo, G. J., 2010. An empirical analysis of auditor independence in the banking industry, *The Accounting Review*, Vol 85, Issue 6, 2011 – 2046.
- xxi. Knechel W. R., Krishnam, V., Pevzner, M., 2013. Audit quality: Insights from the Academic Literature *Auditing, A Journal of Practice & Theory*, 32 (1), 385-421.
- xxii. Lee T.H., Azham M.A., 2018. The evolution of auditing: An Analysis of the Historical Development, *Journal of Modern Accounting and Auditing*, Vol 4, Issue 12, David Publishing Company, Inc.
- xxiii. Liu, C. C., & Ryan, S. G., 1995. The effect of bank loan portfolio composition on the market reaction to and anticipation of loan loss provisions, *Journal of Accounting Research*, Vol 3, Issue 1, 77 – 94.
- xxiv. Liu, C. C., Ryan, S. G., & Wahlen, J. M., 1997. Differential valuation implications of loan loss provisions across banks and fiscal quarters, *Accounting Review*, Vol 72, Issue 1, 133–146.
- xxv. Maines, L. A., Bartov, E., Fairfield, P., Hirst, D. E., Iannaconi, T. E., Mallett, R. & Vincent, L., 2003. Evaluating concepts-based vs rules-based approaches to standard setting, *Accounting Horizons*, Vol 17, Issue 1, 73 – 89.
- xxvi. Mock, T. J., & Samet, M., 1982. A multi attribute model for audit evaluation, *Journal of Accounting Research*, 99 – 112.
- xxvii. Nunnally, J. C., & Bernstein, I. H., 1987. Chapter 7: the assessment of reliability, *Psychometric theory*.
- xxviii. Palmrose, Z.V., 2011. Review of studies on audit quality, *International Conference on Humanities, Society and Culture, IPEDR Vol.20, IACSIT Press, Singapore*.
- xxix. Pérez, D., Salas-Fumas, V., & Saurina, J., 2008. Earnings and capital management in alternative loan loss provision regulatory regimes, *European Accounting Review*, Vol 17, 423-445.
- xxx. Scholes, M. S., Wilson, G. P., & Wolfson, M. A., 1990. Tax planning, regulatory capital planning, and financial reporting strategy for commercial banks, *Review of Financial Studies*, Vol 3, Issue 4, 625–650.
- xxxi. Schroeder, M. S., Solomon, I., & Vickrey, D., 1986,. Audit quality: The perceptions of Audit-Committee Chairpersons and Audit Partners, *A Journal of Practice and Theory*, Vol 5, 86 – 94.
- xxxii. Schipper, K., 1989. Commentary on earnings management, *Accounting Horizons*, Vol 3, Issue 1, 91 – 102.
- xxxiii. Sherolli Jr, X., 2016. Determinants of Audit Quality in the USA Banking Sector, *International Hellenic University, USA*.
- xxxiv. Sutton, S. G., & Lampe, J. C., 1991. A framework for evaluating process quality for Audit Engagements, *Accounting and Business Research*, Vol 21, 275 – 288.
- xxxv. Treadway, J. C., 1987. Report of the national commission on fraudulent financial reporting, *The Commission*.
- xxxvi. Warming-Rasmussen, B., & Jensen, L., 1998. Quality Dimensions in External Audit Services – An External User Perspective, *European Accounting Review*, Vol 7, Issue 1, 65–82.
- xxxvii. Wooten, T. C., 2003. Research about audit quality, *The CPA Journal*, 73(1), 48.
- xxxviii. Yasar, A., 2013. Big Four Auditor’s Audit Quality and Earnings Management: Evidence from Turkish Stock Market, *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, Vol 4 (17).